

IN VITRO ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF EXTRACTS OF *PSIDIUM GUAJAVA*

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ABSTRACT

The antifungal activity of aqueous and organic (acetone and methanol) leaf extracts of *Psidium guajava* was evaluated against some common pathogenic fungi using the paper disc diffusion method. All the extracts were active against the test organisms with the methanol extracts showing the highest activity against *Candida albicans* (26 mm zone of inhibition) *Cryptococcus neoformans* (22 mm zone of inhibition) and, *Fusarium oxysporum* (18 mm zone of inhibition), followed by the acetone extracts against *Penicillium digitatum* (16 mm zone of inhibition) and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (12 mm zone of inhibition) at 250 mg/ml. The aqueous extracts demonstrated the lowest activity (8 mm zone of inhibition) against *Penicillium digitatum* and 6 mm zone of inhibition against *Aspergillus fumigatus* at 250 mg/ml. Preliminary phytochemical studies revealed that the leaves contained the phytoconstituents tannins, flavonoids and anthraquinones. The activity of the extracts was stable at high temperatures and at acidic pH, but decreased at alkaline pH. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and the Minimum Fungicidal Concentration (MFC) of the extracts ranged between 12.5 – 150mg/ml. The plant contains chemicals substances that can be used in the formulation of very potent antifungal agents that can be used for the treatment of mycotic infections.

KEY WORDS: Phytochemicals, Antifungal activity, MIC, MFC, mycotic infections

INTRODUCTION

Opportunistic fungal infections represent a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in immunocompromised patients, including those with AIDS, cancer and organ transplants (Fisher-Hoch and Hutwagner, 1995, Salama *et al.* 2001). Despite the increase in fungal infections, therapeutic options are very limited and are often unsatisfactory because of elevated toxicity and an inability to eradicate infections, and in recent times, increase in resistance to antifungal agents including Amphotericin B (AMB), fluconazole and itraconazole by many fungal species (Sheehan *et al.* 1999, Masoko and Eloff, 2005). This therefore, highlights the need for search of new antifungal agents with potent and broad spectrum fungicidal activities for the effective management of these infections (Graybill, 1989; Franklin and Snow, 1989; Prescott *et al.* 2002). Plant sources may be safer alternative sources for antifungal agents.

P. guajava (Family: Myrtaceae), commonly called common guava (England), guayaba (Spain), goiaba or goiabeira (Polland), goyave (France), Jambu burung (Malaysia), Perala (India-Sans) or gua (Ghana) is a small tropical tree that grows up to 35 feet tall; it has spreading branches and smooth bark (CIRAD-FLHOR/IPGRI, 2000). In Nigeria the common names include; ugwoba (Igbo), guafa (Yoruba), gwaaba (Hausa) and woba (Efik) (Zakaria and Mustafa, 1994). The plant has leathery leaves that are opposite oblong-elliptic and have pronounced veins. When crushed they are aromatic. The flowers are white and somewhat fragrant (Ticzon, 1997). Guava is widely grown for its fruit in the tropics. It has a distinctive fresh aroma with a sweet musk odor and the vitamin C content is higher than in citrus. The juicy, fruit pulp is used in drinks or made into jelly. The fruits are also reported to contain saponin, oleanolic acid, and the flavonoids; guaijavarin and quercitin. The roots have also been reported to possess tannins (Zakaria and Mustafa, 1994). The plant has crooked branches, opposite leaves and white flowers. Various uses of different parts of the plant have been reported. Then in India, South Africa, Senegal and Ghana, *P. guajava* fruits are locally used as astringent and antiseptic. The fruits have

also been used to prepare juice (industrial), pulp eaten fresh or cooked, and used to prepare jellies, syrups, ice-creams and preserves and as effective remedy against diarrheas and digestive disorders.

Table 1. Antifungal activity of *P. guajava* against some fungi

Test organisms	Extract	conc. (mg/ml)/zone of inhibition (mm)						
		50	100	150	200	250	Nst (50mg/ml)	Fuc (50mg/ml)
<i>A. niger</i>	WE	-	8	8	10	12	18	-
	AE	-	6	8	10	12	NA	NA
	ME	6	8	10	12	14	NA	NA
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	WE	-	-	-	6	6	14	-
	AE	-	6	8	10	12	NA	NA
	ME	6	8	10	14	16	NA	NA
<i>A. flavus</i>	WE	-	-	6	8	10	16	-
	AE	-	6	8	10	12	NA	NA
	ME	-	6	8	10	14	NA	NA
<i>P. digitatum</i>	WE	-	-	-	6	8	14	18
	AE	-	6	10	12	16	NA	NA
	ME	6	8	10	14	18	NA	NA
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	WE	-	-	6	8	10	18	20
	AE	-	-	6	10	12	NA	NA
	ME	-	6	8	10	18	NA	NA
<i>Cr. neoformans</i>	WE	-	6	8	8	12	16	8
	AE	-	6	10	14	14	NA	NA
	ME	6	8	12	18	22	NA	NA
<i>B. cinerea</i>	WE	-	-	-	6	10	20	12
	AE	-	2	5	7	9	NA	NA
	ME	3	7	12	14	15	NA	NA
<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>	WE	-	-	-	6	6	8	6
	AE	-	-	6	8	12	NA	NA
	ME	-	-	6	8	14	NA	NA
<i>C. albicans</i>	WE	-	-	-	6	8	14	4
	AE	6	8	10	12	14	NA	NA
	ME	8	16	18	24	26	NA	NA

Key: WE = water extract; AE = acetone extract; ME = methanol extract; NA = not applicable; Nst = nystatin; Fuc = Fuchsin; - = no measurable zone

Leaf decoction are used as a remedy for coughs, throat and chest ailments, gargled to relieve oral ulcers and inflamed gums, as an emmenagogue and vermifuge, treatment of leucorrhoea; it has been effective against vomiting and diarrhea in cholera patients. Also used to clean wounds and accelerate healing (Madagascar).

The anti-bacterial activity and hypoglycemic properties of guava has earlier been reported (Ben-Erik van *et al.* 1997). In Brazil and Nigeria the leaves are used in the treatment of skin infections, eczema and atopic dermatitis (Conway, 2001). Filamentous fungi can cause invasive infections, which are associated with high morbidity and mortality, particularly in immunocompromised patients, despite antifungal

chemotherapy ((Mauch *et al.* 1988; Denning, 1996; Marr *et al.* 2002; Meyers, 1990; Patterson *et al.* 2000). This study was carried out in order to investigate the antifungal activity of the plant against some common pathogenic fungi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fresh leaves of *P.guajava* were collected from the river side gardens in Yola North Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria and were identified and authenticated in the Department of Biological Sciences; School of Pure and Applied Sciences, Federal University of Technology, Yola; Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Table 2. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Fungicidal Concentration (MFC) of the methanolic extracts of the plant against the test fungi

Test organism	MIC (mg/ml)	MFC (mg/ml)
<i>A. niger</i>	100	150
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	100	150
<i>A. flavus</i>	150	150
<i>P. digitatum</i>	100	150
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	50	50
<i>Cr. neoformans</i>	25	50
<i>B. cinerea</i>	150	150
<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>	50	100
<i>C. albicans</i>	12.5	25

Test Organisms

C.andida albicans, *Aspergillus niger*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. flavus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Trychophyton mentagrophytes* and *Botrytis cinerea* were laboratory isolates and saboraud dextrose agar (SDA) (Oxoid) and other reagents (analytical grade) and glass wares used for the purpose of this study were all obtained from the Microbiology Laboratory, Department of Microbiology, Federal University of Technology, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria. The antifungal agents; nystatin and fuchsin, were purchased from Jimex pharmaceutical stores Jimeta, Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Preparation of Extracts

The plant extracts were prepared using the method earlier described by Ahmad and Beg, (2001) with minor modification. The fresh leaves were shade dried to constant weight for 5 days, coarsely powdered using mortar and pestle and further reduced to powder using electric blender and stored in closed bottles. Twenty grammes (20 g) each of the ground plant part was soaked separately in 100 ml, water, methanol and acetone at room temperature (30 – 32 °C) for 24 h with manual agitation of the flask using a sterile glass rod after every 6 h. After 24 h, each of the extracts was filtered using a clean sterile muslin cloth and then using Whatman No. 1 filter paper. All the extracts were concentrated using a rotatory evaporator at 40 °C and then kept in the fridge prior to use.

Determination of phytochemical constituents

The freshly prepared extract was subjected to standard phytochemical analyses for different constituents such as tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids, anthraquinones, glycosides, saponins and phenols as earlier described (Odebiyi and Sofowora 1999).

Assay of antifungal activity

The paper disc diffusion method as described by Irobi and Daramola (1994) was used with slight modification. 10 ml Saboraud dextrose agar (SDA) (Oxoid) was dispensed into Petri dishes and allowed to solidify. A micropipette was used to introduce 0.1ml of the spore or conidia suspensions adjusted to 10^5 – 10^7 cells/ml using haemocytometre, was added on to the agar plate, and spread with glass rod spreader under sterile conditions. Sterilised discs (6 mm, Whatman No 1) were prepared

by soaking in different concentrations of the extracts (50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 mg/ml) for 6 h in bijou bottles. The discs were then removed and allowed to dry in a sterile Petri dish, then stored in screw capped bottles for further use. To assay for antifungal activity, five of the discs impregnated with different concentrations of the extract were placed on a fungal spore or conidia seeded plate with the help of sterile forceps. Discs impregnated with nystatin and fuchsin (50 mg/ml each) was used for comparison, while discs soaked in sterilised distilled water only without extracts were used as control. Three replicates were produced for each fungus. Culture plates containing *C. albicans* were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h while other culture plates containing the rest of the fungi were incubated at room temperature (32 – 35 °C) for 48-72 h. Antifungal activity was determined by measurement of the zone of inhibition around the discs after the period of incubation.

Key: NT = non treated extract; deg = °C
 Fig 1. Effect of temperature (°C) on antifungal activity of *Psidium guajava* (t-test on statistical software package SPSS; p < 0.05)

Fig 2. Effect of pH on the antifungal activity of *Psidium guajava* (t-test on statistical software package SPSS; p < 0.05)

Determination of minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Fungicidal Concentration (MFC)

The MIC was determined using the agar dilution method described by Collins and Lyne (1970). Varying concentrations (300.0, 250.0, 200.0, 150.0, 100.0, 50.0, 25.0 and 12.5 mg/ml), of the extracts were prepared and incorporated into Sabouraud dextrose agar. The plates were incubated at 25 °C for 48 h and inhibition of growth was noted. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs) were recorded after 48 h.

To determine the MFC, plates which did not show any growth after 48 h from the MIC determination were further incubated for 72 h and after incubation, the concentration at which no visible growth was seen was noted as the minimum fungicidal concentration.

Effect of Temperature and pH on antimicrobial activity of extracts

Five milliliters of 250 mg/ml of methanol extracts were constituted in test tubes and treated at 4 °C in the refrigerator and 60 and 100 °C in a water bath for 1 h and tested for antimicrobial activity.

To determine the effect of pH, the methanol extracts (250 mg/ml) were treated at pH ranges of 2 to 10 using 1N HCl and 1N NaOH solutions respectively in series of test tubes for 1h. After the 1 h period of acid-base treatment, the extracts were again neutralized using 1N HCl and 1N NaOH solutions as the case may be and then tested for antifungal activity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary phytochemical analysis revealed that the plant possessed the phytoconstituents tannins, flavonoids and anthraquinones. Plants have been known to possess bioactive constituents as protective substances against bacteria, fungi, viruses and pests (Marjorie, 1999). Presence of tannins in the leaves has also been reported (Nadkarni and Nadkarni, 1999). The stem bark has been reported to contain tannins and to possess antibacterial activity. The methanol extracts of the plant demonstrated the highest activity compared to the aqueous and acetone extracts. The highest activity (26 mm zone of inhibition) was demonstrated against *C. albicans* followed by those against *Cr. neoformans* (22 mm zone of inhibition) at 250 mg/ml (Table 1). The demonstration of antifungal activity against *C. albicans* and *Cr. neoformans* is a further justification for the application of the leaves in the treatment of vaginal irritation and discharges (Dutta, *et al.* 2000). The highest activities (14 and 16 mm zone of inhibition) was demonstrated against *Cr. neoformans* and *P. digitatum* respectively by the acetone extracts at 250 mg/ml while the least activity (6 mm zone of inhibition) against *Trichophyton* spp and *A. fumigatus* was demonstrated by the aqueous extracts at 250 mg/ml. The activity of the extracts against these fungi also gives scientific bases on the application of the infusion of the leaves in the treatment of eczema and other skin infections (Dutta, *et al.* 2000). The differences observed in the activities of the various extracts may be as a result of their varying degrees of solubility in the different solvents. It has been reported that different solvents have different solubility capacities for different phytoconstituents (Marjorie, 1999). The exhibition of antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, *Trichophyton* spp, *Cr. neoformans* and the other fungi is a very significant outcome because it is an indication that there is possibility of sourcing alternative antibiotic substances in these plants for the development of newer antifungal agents that will be very effective against candidiasis (caused by *C. albicans*), systemic mycosis (*Aspergillus* spp), ring worm infections (caused by *Trichophyton* spp) and cryptococcosis (*Cr. neoformans*) that are rapidly becoming refractile to chemotherapy with the standard antifungal agents (Masoko and Eloff, 2005) Table 2 showed the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum fungicidal concentration (MFC) of the extracts. The result showed that the MICs and MFCs values were in the range of 12.5 – 150 mg/ml. The lowest MIC and MFC values of 12.5 mg/ml was demonstrated against *C. albicans*, while the highest MIC and MFC value of 150 mg/ml was demonstrated against *A. flavus* and *B. cinerea*. Low MIC and MFC values are indication of efficacy of the plant, while high MIC and MFC values are indication of inefficiency of the antifungal agents. Results of the investigation of the effects of temperature and pH on the activity of the extracts are shown in Fig 1 and 2. The result showed that increase in temperature from 4 to 100 °C had no significant effect on the activity of the extracts but acidic pH enhanced the activity of the extracts while, alkaline pH reduced the activity (using t-test on statistical software package SPSS; $p < 0.05$). At 4 and 30 °C the activity of the methanol extracts against *C. albicans* was 26 mm zone of inhibition at 250 mg/ml, and at 60 and 100 °C the activities were 26 and 28 mm zone of inhibition respectively (Fig 1). The fact that the activity of the extracts was unaffected with increase in temperature was an indication that the bioactive components present in this plant may be heat stable. Stability of phytoconstituents to temperature has earlier been reported (Doughari 2007). At pH 4.3 (untreated), the highest activity (22 and 26 mm) was demonstrated by the extracts against *Cr. neoformans* and *C. albicans* respectively at 250 mg/ml and 24 and 28 mm (zone of inhibition) at pH 2 for the two organisms respectively. The activities however reduced to 8 mm zone of inhibition (*Cr. neoformans*) and 12 mm zone of inhibition (*C. albicans*) at pH 10 (Fig 2). The effect of pH on the activity of phytoconstituents has earlier been reported (Molan, 1992; Ticzon, 1997; Doughari, 2007)

The demonstration of activity against the different category of pathogenic fungi by leaves of *P. guajava* is an indication that the plant can be used to source newer group of antifungal substances that can be used to develop more effective antifungal agents, and also justifies its local usage for the treatment of skin infections. The plant can therefore be used for the treatment of mycotic infections such as candidiasis, ringworm and cryptococcosis and other systemic mycoses. Further research however needs to be carried

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out in order to determine the antifungal activity of the plant against a wider group of pathogenic fungi, and to investigate its toxicological properties and also further purification of the extracts should be carried out with a view to producing safer antifungal chemotherapeutic agents for man use.

REFERENCES

Ahmad, I., Beg, A.Z. (2001). Antimicrobial and phytochemical studies on 45 Indian medicinal plants against multi-resistant human pathogens. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 74: 87-91.

Ben-Erik van, W., Bosch van, O., Gericke, N. (1997). *Medicinal plants of South Africa*. Briza Publications Pretoria, SA. pp 1-5.

CIRAD-FLHOR/IPGRI. (2000). *Fruits from America: an ethnobotanical inventory*. <http://www.cirad.fr/>

Collins, C.H. and Lyne, P. M. (1970). *Microbiological Methods*. 3rd Edition. Butterworth and Co. Ltd. pp 414-427.

Conway, P. (2001). *Tree medicine-a comprehensive guide to the healing power of over 10 trees*. Judy Piatkus Publishers Ltd. pp 213-2177.

Denning, D.W. (1996). Therapeutic outcome in invasive aspergillosis. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* 23: 608-615.

Doughari, J.H. (2007). Antifungal activity of extracts of *Mangifera indica*L. *Journal of Research in Physical Science*. Manuscript No. JRPS 2007-08 (in press) [http:// www.irdionline.com](http://www.irdionline.com)

Dutta, B.K, Imtiaz, R., Das, T.K. (2000). In vitro study on antifungal property of common fruit plants. *Biomedicine* 20(3): 187-189.

Fisher-Hoch, S.P., Hutwagner, L. (1995). Opportunistic candidiasis: an epidemic of the 1980's. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 21: 897-904.

Franklin, T.J. and Snow, C.A. (1989). *Biochemistry of antimicrobial action*. 4th edn. Chapman and Hall pp 134-1551

Graybill, J.R. (1989). New antifungal agents. *European Journal of Clinical Microbiology Infectious Diseases* 5: 402-412.

Irobi, O.N. and Daramola, S. O. (1994). Antifungal activities of crude extracts of *Mitracarpus villosus* (Rubiaceae). *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 38: 604 – 610.

Marr, K. A., Carter, R.A., Crippa, F., Wald, A. and Corey, L (2002). Epidemiology and outcome of mould infections in hematopoietic stem cell transplant recipients. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 34:909-917.

Marjorie, M.C. (1999). Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* 12(4): 564-582.

Masoko, P. and Eloff, J.N. (2005). The diversity of antifungal compounds of six South African *Terminalia* species (Combretaceae) determined by bioautography. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 4(12): 1425-1431.

Mauch, F., Mauch-Mani, B. and Boller, T. (1988). Antifungal hydrolases in pea tissue. II. Inhibition of fungal growth by combinations of chitinase and B-1,3-glucanase. *Plant Physiology* 3: 936-942.

Meyers, J. D. (1990). Fungal infections in bone marrow transplant patients. *Semin. Oncol.* 17:10-13.

Doughari, J.H *et al*: Continental J. Microbiology 1: 1 - 7, 2007.

Molan, P.C. (1992). The antibacterial activity of honey 1. The nature of antibacterial activity. *Bee World*. 73: 59 – 76.

Nadkarni, K.M. and Nadkarni, A.K. (1999). Allopathic, Homeopathic, Naturopathic and Home remedies. *Indian Materia Medica*. 1: 81-89.

Odebiyi, A. and Sofowora, A.E. (1999). Phytochemical screenings of Nigerian medicinal plants part II, *Lyodia* 41: 234-246.

Patterson, T. F., W. R. Kirkpatrick, M. White, J. W. Hiemenz, J. R. Wingard, B. Dupont, M. G. Rinaldi, D. A. Stevens, and J. R. Graybill. (2000). Invasive aspergillosis. Disease spectrum, treatment practices, and outcomes. *I3 Aspergillus Study Group Medicine (Baltimore)*. 79:250-260.

Prescott, L., Harley, J. and Klein, D.A. (2002). *Microbiology*. 5th edn. McGraw-Hill. pp 820-950.

Salama, S.M., Atwal, H., Gandhi, A., Simon, J., Poglod, M., Montaseri, H., Khan, J.K., Furukawa, T., Saito, H. and Micetich, R.G. (2001). *In vitro* and *In vivo* activities of Syn2836, Syn2869, Syn2903, and Syn2921: New series of triazole antifungal agents, *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 45: 2420-2426

Sheehan, D.J., Hoelscher, A.C. and Sibley, M.C. (1999). Current and emerging azole antifungal agents. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* 12: 40-79.

Ticzon, R. (1997). *Ticzon herbal medicine encyclopaedia*. Romeo R. Ticzon publishing. Phillipines.2: 231-232

Zakaria, M.M. and Mustafa, A. (1994). *Traditional Malay medicinal plants*. Penerbit Fajar Bakti Sdn. 65: 967-69.

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